

Impact of Multimodal Interventions to Enhance HPV Vaccination in an Ambulatory OBGYN Department

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Background

- Human papillomavirus is the most prevalent sexually transmitted infection in the United States
- High-risk HPV is the source of over 90% of cervical cancer and 70% of oropharyngeal cancer
- The HPV vaccine is available, proven safe, and effective in preventing HPV related cancers, including cervical cancer
- Most young adults are not fully vaccinated
- While early prevention is key, vaccinating young adults is beneficial

Purpose

To increase the HPV vaccination rate to 20% for patients ages 18 to 26 in an ambulatory OBGYN department by February 2022 through the implementation and evaluation of a standardized workflow algorithm using multimodal clinic interventions

Methods

- Design: Prospective Pre/Post survey
- Setting: Ambulatory OBGYN clinic at a managed healthcare system in Southern California
- Participants: MDs, NPs, CNMs, PAs, RNs, LVNs, MAs
- Data Collection: 12 Weeks
- Outcome Measure: # of patients that received the HPV vaccine
- Process Measure: # of patients that declined the HPV vaccine
- Pre-post survey to assess participant knowledge

Modified Iowa Model-Revised for Evidence-Based Practice

Results

- HPV vaccination rate remained at baseline by project completion, encouraging increase in rate was seen after staff education and team huddles
- Total patients eligible to receive the HPV vaccine N=270
- Total patients that received the HPV vaccine 9% (n=25)
- Total patients that declined the HPV vaccine 23% (n=63)

Knowledge Survey

- Of 114 staff invited, 28 participants pre-education and 14 participants post-education responded
- 86% agreed/strongly agreed post-education, HPV vaccine series does not need to be restarted if dose is missed compared to 71% pre-education
- 93% pre-education and 86% post-education agreed/strongly agreed they would recommend the HPV vaccine
- > 90% of respondents aware HPV vaccine available in OBGYN dept.

Healthcare Providers and Staff response to Questions About HPV and HPV Vaccination

Question	Pre-education N=28	Post-education N=14
Q1: HPV vaccine prevents HPV-causing cancer and genital warts.	89	85
Q2: How likely are you to recommend the HPV vaccine?	93	86
Q3: Three dose HPV vaccine is recommended for patients ages 15 to 26 years.	100	92
Q4: HPV vaccine series does not need to be restarted if the 2 nd or 3 rd dose is missed.	71	86
Q5: Are you aware that the HPV vaccine is available in the OBGYN department?	96	93

Discussion

- Findings consistent with previous research re: low HPV vaccination rates in OBGYN clinic
- Explore provider/staff factors impacting HPV vaccination rates (i.e., personal beliefs and practices)
- Raised awareness re: need to improve staff recommendation of HPV vaccine
- Team engagement and leadership support are vital for quality initiatives

Limitations

- Outcomes may not be generalized beyond OBGYN setting, due to the small number of participants
- Provider/Staff education or experience and patient demographics were not collected

Clinical Implications

- HCP/Staff benefit from ongoing education about recommending HPV vaccine
- Evidence-based findings must be incorporated into patient care
- Continuing education about benefits and efficacy of HPV immunization essential for HCP/staff
- Need routine updates on HPV guidelines and practices

Conclusions

- Reinforce standardized protocol and guidelines re: HPV immunization
- Address patient/provider barriers to HPV vaccination, reasons patients decline
- Future research needed to support interventions that improve HPV vaccination rates in OBGYN clinic

References upon request Ajayi0323@gmail.com

